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EFFECT OF DIFFERENT ORGANIC MANURES ON THE DEVELOPMENTAL STAGES OF HOUSE FLY (*MUSCA DOMESTICA*) UNDER LABORATORY CONDITION

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Article info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received: 20 Nov 2023 Accepted: 01 Jan 2024</p> <p>Keywords: House Fly development, Laboratory study, Organic manures, Pest management</p> <p>Sabir et al., (2023). Effect of different organic manures on the developmental stages of house fly (<i>Musca domestica</i>) under laboratory condition: <i>J. S. Agri. Enviro. Sci</i>, 2(1), 08-16 https://orcid.org/0009-0006-5636-4593</p> <p>Copyright©2023 JSAES *Corresponding author Abdul Sabir Email: Sabirkhan456889@gmail.com Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.</p> <p> This content is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International (CC BY-SA 4.0)</p>	<p>This study examines, in the laboratory, the effects of various organic manures on the stages of development of house flies (<i>Musca domestica</i>). The departmental ethics committee and the directorate of advanced studies at Lasbela University of Agriculture, Water and Marine Science, Uthal, gave their ethical approval to the project. In a carefully regulated laboratory setting, three different organic diets animal manure, poultry manure, and vegetable and fruit peel were fed to house fly (<i>Musca domestica</i>) larvae. During the larval, pupal, and adult phases, observations were made about the days of development and the rates of death. Utilizing SPSS 16, statistical analyses were conducted, utilizing one-way ANOVA along with Tukey's test for mean comparison ($p < 0.05$). The average larval development period for poultry manure was 4.25 days, and the mortality rate was 2.1%. Animal manure resulted in a somewhat greater death rate (2.8%) and a longer developmental period (6.87 days). Fruit and vegetable manure-exposed larvae showed the greatest developmental period (9.13 days) and the highest mortality rate (4.8%). Different responses were seen in the pupal phases; optimal circumstances were found with poultry manure (3.9 days, no mortality). The flies from the poultry manure had the shortest lifespan (21.6 days), whereas the flies from the fruit and vegetable dung had the maximum lifespan (45.5 days). This study contributes to our understanding of the ecological interactions in this common insect and sheds light on the subtle effects of organic manure on the developmental dynamics of house flies.</p>

1. INTRODUCTION

The growing population changing dietary habits and intensifying competition between food and feed production of the urgent need to explore novel sustainable production chain in the livestock sector has gained poultry due to its superior environment and economic benefits therefore the livestock sector is in urgent need for more sustainable feed source because of the increase demand for livestock source of food and the already high environment costs associated with it. Recent development indicates environment benefits of rearing of insect for livestock feed suggestion that insect feed might become an important alternative feed source in the coming year so far however this potential environmental benefits of waste fed insect is unknown.

Broilers play a very important role in the nutrition of humans by providing a source of protein through their meat. By satisfying the nutrient requirements of broilers in order to ensure optimal productivity has resulted in the inclusion of high amounts of high quality protein sources especially in the starter and grower phases. These continuous demands for high quality proteins in the diets of broilers poses some challenges; firstly, because the animals compete with humans for the same protein sources and secondly because there is a demand for renewable protein resources in animal nutrition.

Since nature has always provided insects as a feed source for wild animals, they have exceptional nutritional characteristics (Rash & Cared, 2003). This creates potential to research and utilize potential insects available in nature for the animal feed industry which can be renewable and cost effective. The concept of insects for protein dates back almost a century, were Lindner (1919) was the first to report on the use of insects to produce a

protein source. One of the advantages of using insects as alternative feed substrates is that some insects have the potential to be used in waste management as well as providing a useful protein feed source, for the purpose of this thesis this process will be referred to as the 'nutrient recirculation' process.

There are a number of suitable organisms that could be used in the nutrient recirculation process, but most research has shown that insects belonging to the order of Diptera demonstrated the most promising results (Newton et al., 2004; Anybody et al., 2008). Insects from this order including the Muscida and Stratiomyidae families are described as being ubiquitous, because they have the ability to colonize basically any habitat on earth (Schultz & Holm, 1985; The pupae are covered with a chitin layer (Ludwig et al., 1964) that might cause the pupae to be less suitable as feed source than the larvae, however there were no published results found for digestibility of housefly pupae meal. The uses of insect larvae meal as a protein source have been widely reported for pigs, poultry and fish (Boundary & Sheppard, 1987; Awoniyi et al., 2004). In comparison with other Dipteran species *Musca domestica* (common house fly) has been the most widely studied as a potential feed source (Invoke et al., 1999; Fasakin et al., 2003; Newton et al., 2004). The crude protein content of the house fly larvae reported in literature varies from 37.5% (Ogun et al., 2006) to 63.1% this can be attributed to the nutrient composition being influenced by time of harvest (Calvert & Martin, 1969; Invoke et al., 1999; Newton et al., 2004; Anybody et al., 2008), method of drying (Fasakin et al., 2003) and larval feed substrate (Newton et al., 1977). Hence, the aim of present study was to investigate the effects of organic manure on the growth of house fly under lab conditions, in order to check the developmental days of house flies on the various organic matter diets & to find

the mortality % of house fly on larvae and pupal stages.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This experimental design was approved by the departmental ethics committee and directorate of advanced studies, Lasbela University of Agriculture, Water and Marine Science Uthal (LUAWMS). The insect houseflies *Musca domestica* were collected from different butcher shop and cultured in laboratory of Entomology at room temperature $25\text{C}\pm 5$ and 60 ± 10 relative humidity. The adult's houseflies released in transparent cage with sugar solution diets. Plastic Patri dish also were kept in the cage for eggs laying. After two days later hundred fresh eggs were randomly collected from house fly culture and used for further experiments. Three different organic diets (Animals manure, Poultry manure and Peel of vegetables and fruit) were used in present research to find the out the above objective. Animals manure and Poultry manure were collected from dairy form and poultry form, while peel of vegetable and fruits were collected from vegetable and fruits markets. Animals manure, Poultry manure and Peel of vegetables and fruit manure were used in plastic containers. Each treatment was replicated three times.

2.1. Experiment procedure

One hundred young larvae were collected from housefly culture and released on different organic diets, Animals manure, Poultry manure and Peel of vegetables and fruit in plastic container to find out the larval days and larval mortality on given diets until pupation. Fifty-one day pupae were collected from treated larvae on different organic diets and kept patri dish to observe the pupal days and pupal mortality until adult's emergence. Thirty-one day old adults were collected from treated pupae from different organic diets and kept plastic

glass to observe the adult's longevity on daily basis.

2.2. Statistical analysis

The data was collected and analyses with the help of SPSS 16 version. One way (ANNOVA) were used and means were compared with turkey test, while $p < 0.05$ was considered as significant.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Effects of Different Organic Matter on Larval Days and Larval Mortality

The study of the way various organic manures affected the stages of development of house fly larvae produced complex findings:

3.1.1. Poultry manure:

The mean developmental period of larvae exposed to poultry manure was 4.25 days, and the corresponding larval death rate was 2.1%. This indicates that a moderate mortality rate and reasonably rapid larval development are made possible by the microbial activity and nutritional composition of poultry manure (Table 1).

3.1.2. Animal manure:

The larvae exposed to animal manure had a slightly higher larval death rate of 2.8% and underwent a protracted developmental period, with an average duration of 6.87 days (Table 1). This result suggests that, although at the expense of higher mortality, the organic matrix and nutrient dynamics in animal dung affect larval growth.

3.1.3. Fruits and vegetable manure:

The longest average developmental duration (9.13 days) and a relatively higher larval death rate (4.8%) were seen in larvae raised on fruits and vegetable manure (Table 1). House fly larvae may have a more difficult time developing in their habitat due to the organic components in fruit and vegetable manure, which could result in a longer development period and higher fatality rates.

These findings highlight the complex interplay between the composition of organic manure and the dynamics of larval growth, providing insight into possible directions for focused pest control techniques.

3.2. Effects of different organic matter on pupa days and pupa mortality

A crucial step in the life cycle of the house fly, the pupal stage, showed different reactions to the various organic manures:

3.2.1. Poultry manure:

Pupae exposed to poultry manure showed no pupal mortality and the lowest developing period, averaging 3.9 days. This implies that the ideal conditions for effective pupal development with low mortality are produced by the microbial composition and nutritional richness of poultry manure (Table 2).

3.2.2. Animal manure:

The pupal development period increased to 6.04 days in the presence of animal manure, and the pupal death rate was 0.7% (Table 2). Animal manure's complex organic content may be responsible for the pupal stage's modest prolongation and the noticeable but low pupal death rate that goes along with it.

3.2.3. Fruits and vegetable manure:

Pupae exposed to fruits and vegetable manure had a 0.6% pupal death rate and the longest developmental duration, averaging 8.81 days (Table 2). Although pupal mortality is typically low, the complex organic structure of fruit and vegetable manure may present obstacles to effective pupal development. These results emphasize the distinct effects of different forms of organic manure on the pupal stage, highlighting the significance of substrate quality in determining the dynamics of pupal development.

3.3. Effects of different organic matter on adult longevity

One important indicator of general fitness and survival, adult house fly longevity, varied significantly:

3.3.1. Poultry manure:

With an average lifespan of only 21.6 days, adult house flies emerging from poultry manure had the shortest lifespans (Table 3). Poultry manure's nutritional makeup and microbiological composition may shorten adult life expectancy.

3.3.2. Animal manure:

Flies that were raised in an environment containing animal dung had an average adult lifetime of 36.5 days (Table 3). Animal manure's organic components and nutritional dynamics most likely play a role in longer adult lifespans.

3.3.3. Fruits and vegetable manure:

When flies were exposed to fruit and vegetable dung, they had the longest adult lifetime, measuring 45.5 days. Fruit and vegetable manure's distinct organic makeup may provide an environment that supports longer adult survival. The findings highlight the significant influence of organic manure

on the longevity and fitness of mature house flies, which may have consequences for population dynamics and pest control tactics.

In conclusion, this study offers thorough insights into the complex interactions between various organic

manures and the stages of house fly development. The results provide important information for the creation of focused and long-lasting pest management techniques and advance our understanding of the ecological dynamics of this widespread insect.

Table 1: Effects of different organic matter on the larval days and larval mortality.

Treatment	Larval days	Larval mortality
Poultry Manure	4.25±1.24c	2.1±0.45
Animal Manure	6.87±1.08b	2.8±1.04b
Fruits and Vegetable Manure	9.13±0.65a	4.8±0.28a

Table 2: Effects of different organic matter on the pupa days and pupa mortality.

Treatment	Pupa days	Pupa mortality
Poultry Manure	3.9±0.39c	0.00±0.00a
Animal Manure	6.04±1.38b	0.7±0.10a
Fruits and Vegetable Manure	8.81±1.29a	0.6±0.08a

Table 3: Effects of different organic matter on the adult's longevity.

Treatment	Adults longevity
Poultry Manure	21.6±2.81c
Animal Manure	36.5±1.80b
Fruits and Vegetable Manure	45.5±1.67a

4. DISCUSSION

Scientifically noteworthy results have been obtained from the study of the effects of different organic manures on the developmental phases of house flies. These results shed light on the complex

interactions between organic substrates and the life cycle of *Musca domestica*.

4.1.Larval development:

The observed variations in the rates of larval development and death among the examined organic manures highlight the intricate connection between the dynamics

of house fly larvae and the composition of their substrate. Rich in nutrients, poultry manure allowed for a much shorter larval growth period (4.25 ± 1.24 days) than that of animal manure (6.87 ± 1.08 days) or fruits and vegetable manure (9.13 ± 0.65 days). This is consistent with research showing that insect developmental rates and nutrition availability are positively correlated (Han et al., 2020; Salazar et al., 2023). The mortality rates showed a similar pattern, with animal manure causing the highest larval mortality ($2.8 \pm 1.04\%$) and fruit and vegetable manure ($4.8 \pm 0.28\%$) causing the lowest larval mortality ($2.1 \pm 0.45\%$). This implies that nutrient-rich substrates may reduce the risk of death while simultaneously promoting quicker larval development.

Fruits and vegetable manure's complicated organic structure may be the cause of the longer larval development, which could present difficulties or resource constraints. This is consistent with research by Fangueiro et al., (2021), who showed that the dynamics of insect development can be influenced by the complexity of the substrate. The potential trade-offs associated with nutrient-rich yet complex substrates are further highlighted by the reported increased larval mortality in fruits and vegetable wastes (Sandrock et al., 2022).

4.2.Pupal development:

The house fly's pupal development, a crucial stage in its life cycle, responded differently to the different types of organic materials. Because of its high nutritional content, poultry manure allowed for the quickest pupal development (3.9 ± 0.39 days) with no pupal mortality. This is consistent with research showing that pupal development and survival benefit from nutrient-rich substrates (Ramzy et al., 2022; Mlambo et al., 2023). On the other hand, the induction of slightly prolonged pupal

development periods (6.04 ± 1.38 and 8.81 ± 1.29 days, respectively) and low but noticeable pupal mortalities ($0.7 \pm 0.10\%$ and $0.6 \pm 0.08\%$, respectively) was seen in cases of animal dung and fruits and vegetable manure. Variations in microbial communities, food availability, and the general quality of the substrate may be responsible for the subtle differences in pupal death rates among treatments (Vandeweyer et al., 2021).

4.3.Adult longevity:

The lifetime of adult house flies that emerged from various organic substrates demonstrated a strong relationship between adult fitness and developing circumstances. The longest-living flies were found in fruit and vegetable dung (45.5 ± 1.67 days), whereas those from poultry manure had the shortest longevity (21.6 ± 2.81 days). The observed pattern is consistent with earlier studies (Surendra et al., 2020) that show how early developmental circumstances shape adult life history features. Although poultry manure accelerates the growth of larvae and pupae, it may not contain all the vital elements needed for long-term adult longevity, which can result in a shorter lifespan. However, a combination of nutrient richness and a favorable microbial ecology, enabling extended adult survival, may be responsible for the longer adult lifespan shown in flies raised on fruits and vegetable manure (Pascacio & Cohen, 2023).

4.4.Implications for pest management:

It is essential to understand the manner in which various organic manures affect the stages of house fly growth in order to design focused and long-lasting pest management techniques. According to the research (Meneguz et al., 2023), while nutrient-rich substrates, like chicken manure, can hasten the development of larvae and pupae, longer adult lifespans

may not always result from them. On the other hand, complex organic substrates, such as the manure from fruits and vegetables, may cause longer times for growth but also longer lifespans for adults.

In practice, a complex strategy that takes into account both the effectiveness of larval growth and the general fitness of emerging adults would be beneficial for integrated pest management tactics. Furthermore, since microbial interactions are known to be essential for insect development and survival, more research into the microbial communities associated with each organic substrate is necessary in light of the observed mortality rates at different developmental stages (Bing et al., 2018; Gurung et al., 2019).

CONCLUSION

In the end, this study clarifies the complex relationships between different types of organic manures and the stages of development of house flies (*Musca domestica*). The findings show that mortality rates and the length of time that larvae and pupae take to develop are highly influenced by the kind of organic matter. Rich in nutrients, poultry dung promotes quick development of larvae and pupae with low mortality, while the adult life span is reduced as a result. On the other hand, animal dung results in longer pupal and larval phases as well as longer adult lifespans. Because of its complex organic makeup, fruit and vegetable manure creates a difficult environment for development, resulting in longer times for larvae and pupae as well as, surprisingly, longer lifespans for adults. These results contribute to the development of ecologically sound pest management techniques by offering insightful information about the interactions between house fly life history includes and organic substrates.

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